

SYNTHESIS OF 5-SUBSTITUTED-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE CLUBBED PYRAZOLE AND DIHYDROPYRIMIDINE DERIVATIVES AS POTENT BIOACTIVE AGENTS

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Abstract: Through the cyclization of Biginelli-type adducts, a series of 4, fluorophenylpyrazole clubbed 1,3,4-oxadiazole and 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones were synthesised. Spectral methods that are well-established were used to determine their structures. The scaffolds were tested for their antitubercular and antibacterial properties in vitro using microplate alamar blue assay and broth microdilution bioassay, respectively. Compounds 3j and 3l, which contain -OH and -CH₃ groups, were discovered to have minimal cytotoxicity on VERO cells and to be effective antimicrobials and antitubercular possibilities.

Keywords: Antimicrobial, antitubercular, and MIC are the names of the compounds pyrazole, 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one, and 1,3,4-oxadiazole.

INTRODUCTION

Microbe resistance poses a significant challenge to the effective treatment of several infectious illnesses. One of the greatest dangers to human life, according to the World Health Organisation (WHO), is antimicrobial drug resistance (AMR). In the realm of drug development programmes, structural alterations to current medications have shown remarkable outcomes. This leads many to believe that the most effective method for creating new, more powerful drugs is to use a molecular hybridization strategy to create architectural scaffolds. One, two The synthesis of dihydropyrimidines (DHPMs) with diverse bioactivities has recently attracted the interest of many medicinal chemists, and the Biginelli type reaction in particular.³⁻⁵ The varied pharmacological properties of pyrazoles, which include antibacterial, antidepressant, anticonvulsant, antipyretic, anti-influenza, and anticancer actions, have made them a prominent motif in medicinal chemistry and a hub for synthetic heterocycles.⁶⁻⁸ In a multicomponent process, pyrazole derivatives were synthesised using a variety of catalysts, including Sc(OTf)₃, Mg(ClO₄)₂, and H₂SO₄.⁹⁻¹¹ The metabolic profile and receptor-site hydrogen bonding capabilities of oxadiazole have made it a widely used pharmacophore in recent years. Numerous biological actions, including hypoglycaemic, anti-HIV, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and antitubercular effects, are generated by the presence of an azole group in oxadiazole, which increases its lipophilicity and impacts its easy ability to target.^{12,13} Oxadiazole have shown great promise as inhibitors of key biological targets, such as tyrosinase, MAO, and cathepsin K.¹⁴⁻¹⁹

The creation of novel prototypes as powerful antibacterial and antitubercular compounds is a priority, in light of these details and our ongoing efforts to create bioactive agents (20-22). Included in this hybrid molecular framework is the lead of the three medicinally relevant pharmacophores: pyrazole, 1,3,4-oxadiazole, and DHPMs.

EXPERIMENTAL

We got the necessary compounds from Aldrich and E. Merck and proceeded to utilise them unfiltered. Distillation was carried out using Buchi Rotavapor. The Gallenkamp apparatus was used to determine the melting points, and these values have not been revised. To ensure that the reaction was finished and that all compounds were pure, they were run on aluminum-coated TLC plates G60 and F245 (E. Merck) with a 7:3 eluent mixture of hexane and ethyl acetate and seen under ultraviolet light (λ 254 and 365 nm) or iodine vapour. The Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN analyzer was used for the elemental analysis. We used a Bruker Avance II 400 MHz for ¹H NMR spectra and a Varian Mercury-400, 100 MHz for ¹³C NMR spectra. The solvent used was

DMSO-d₆, and we used TMS as a chemical shift reference standard. A Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer was used for infrared spectra recording, and a Shimadzu LCMS 2010 spectrometer for mass spectra scanning.

Ethyl-4-(3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylate (1)

Compound **1** was prepared according to the literature method.²³

4-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-5-carbohydrazide (2)

Compound **1** (0.01 mol) was dissolved in 1,4-dioxane (20 mL) and to this, hydrazine hydrate (99 %, 0.01 mol) was added, followed by the addition of a catalytic amount of

conc. H₂SO₄ and allowed to stir for 5 h at 100 °C. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water. Product, obtained as off-white precipitate, was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol (95 %) to obtain compound **2**.

Yield: 73 %, m.p. 224-225 °C. IR (KBr): 3454, 3340 (N-H), 3060 (C-H_{arom}), 1689 (C=O), 1582 (C=N), 1512 (C=C), 1124 (C-F) cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 1.95 (s, 2H, NH₂), 2.34 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 5.16 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 5.87 (s, 1H, -NHNH₂), 6.91 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 7.30-7.89 (m, 10H, Ar-H), 9.03 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 17.9 (-CH₃), 50.6 (-CH_{pyrimidine}), 123.3 (-CH_{pyrazole}), 118.5-149.1 (Ar-C), 150.3 (C=O, NHCONH), 166.2 (C=O). LCMS (ESI) *m/z*: 406.16 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for C₂₁H₁₉FN₆O₂: C, 62.06; H, 4.71; N, 20.68. Found: C, 62.00; H, 4.62; N, 20.73 %.

General procedure of synthesis of 4-(3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-5-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones (3a-o)

Compound **2** (0.01 mol) with various derivatives of aromatic acids (0.01 mol) were dissolved and stirred in one pot having phosphoryl chloride (POCl₃) (20 mL). The mixture was refluxed at 80 °C for 6 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC), the mixture was slowly quenched on crushed ice. The precipitates were filtered, washed with NaHCO₃ to remove excess POCl₃ trace followed by water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol (95 %) to furnished final compounds.

4-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-5-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3a)

Yield: 71 %, m.p. 241-242 °C. IR (KBr): 3223 (NH), 3061 (C-H_{arom}), 2983 (H-C=C<), 2848 (C-H, CH₃), 1685 (C=O), 1598 (C=N), 1527 (C=C), 1281 (C-O-C), 1122 (C-F) cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 2.36 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 5.18 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.88 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 7.28-8.06 (m, 14H, Ar-H), 8.14 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.10 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 15.1 (-CH₃), 53.6 (C_{pyrimidine}), 123.2 (C_{pyrazole}), 113.5-149.5 (Ar-C), 150.4 (C=O), 160.3, 164.1 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.6 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) *m/z*: 492.17 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for C₂₉H₂₁FN₆O₂: C, 68.28; H, 4.30; N, 17.06. Found: C, 68.19; H, 4.41; N, 17.11 %.

5-(5-(2-Chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-4-(3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3b)

Yield: 65 %, m.p. 218-220 °C. IR (KBr): 3221 (NH), 3062 (C-H_{arom}), 2981 (H-C=C<), 2850 (C-H, CH₃), 1691 (C=O), 1597 (C=N), 1514 (C=C), 1288 (C-O-C), 1107 (C-F), 754 (C-Cl) cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 2.28 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 5.18 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.89 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 7.28-8.20 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 8.28 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.16 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 15.2 (CH₃), 53.5 (C_{pyrimidine}), 123.6 (C_{pyrazole}), 135.3 (C-Cl), 113.2-149.7 (Ar-C), 150.6 (C=O), 160.1, 164.4 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.4 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) *m/z*: 526.13 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for

$C_{28}H_{20}ClFN_6O_2$: C, 68.82; H, 3.83; N, 15.95. Found: C, 63.79; H, 3.85; N, 15.93 %.

5-(5-(3-Chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-4-(3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3c)

Yield: 59 %, m.p. 186-188 °C. IR (KBr): 3222 (NH), 3063 (C-H_{arom}), 2980 (H-C=C<), 2852 (C-H, CH₃), 1691 (C=O), 1599 (C=N), 1517 (C=C), 1280 (C-O-C), 1110 (C-F), 754 (C-Cl) cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 2.30 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 5.16 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.85 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 7.29-8.16 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 8.24 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.15 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 15.0 (CH₃), 53.3 (C_{pyrimidine}), 123.4 (C_{pyrazole}), 135.2 (C-Cl), 113.3-149.5 (Ar-C), 150.7 (C=O), 160.3, 164.6 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.2 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) *m/z*: 526.13 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for $C_{28}H_{20}ClFN_6O_2$: C, 68.82; H, 3.83; N, 15.95. Found: C, 63.90; H, 3.80; N, 15.85 %.

5-(5-(4-Chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-4-(3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3d)

Yield: 63 %, m.p. 225-227 °C. IR (KBr): 3293 (NH), 3066 (C-H_{arom}), 2978 (H-C=C<), 2929 (C-H, CH₃), 1680 (C=O), 1591 (C=N), 1504 (C=C), 1219 (C-O-C), 1155 (C-F), 752 (C-Cl) cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 2.31 (s, 3H, CH₃), 5.26 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.82 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 7.20-8.05 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 8.16 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.04 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 15.3 (CH₃), 53.9 (C_{pyrimidine}), 123.8 (C_{pyrazole}), 135.6 (C-Cl), 113.0-149.7 (Ar-C), 150.5 (C=O), 160.6, 164.4 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.7 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) *m/z*: 526.13 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for $C_{28}H_{20}ClFN_6O_2$: C, 68.82; H, 3.83; N, 15.95. Found: C, 63.75; H, 3.86; N, 15.89 %.

4-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-5-(5-(2-nitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3e)

Yield: 58 %, m.p. 233-235 °C. IR (KBr): 3224 (NH), 3063 (C-H_{arom}), 2981 (H-C=C<), 2862 (C-H, CH₃), 1687 (C=O), 1606 (C=N), 1531 (C=C), 1508 (-N=O), 1234 (C-O-C), 1150 (C-F) cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 2.37 (s, 3H, CH₃), 5.20 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.85 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 7.22-8.15 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 8.20 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.04 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 15.2 (CH₃), 54.0 (C_{pyrimidine}), 122.9 (C_{pyrazole}), 113.0-149.7 (Ar-C), 147.3 (C-NO₂), 150.4 (C=O), 160.2, 164.1 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.5 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) *m/z*: 537.16 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for $C_{28}H_{20}FN_7O_4$: C, 62.57; H, 3.75; N, 18.24. Found: C, 62.53; H, 3.69; N, 18.21 %.

4-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-5-(5-(3-nitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3f)

Yield: 60 %, m.p. 250-252 °C. IR (KBr): 3221 (NH), 3060 (C-H_{arom}), 2985 (H-C=C<), 2854 (C-H, CH₃), 1680 (C=O), 1603 (C=N), 1533 (C=C), 1507 (-N=O), 1231 (C-O-C), 1155 (C-F) cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 2.35 (s, 3H, CH₃), 5.23 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.86 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 7.20-8.21 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 8.29 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.08 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 15.1 (CH₃), 54.4 (C_{pyrimidine}), 123.1 (C_{pyrazole}), 113.4-149.9 (Ar-C), 147.6 (C-NO₂), 150.5 (C=O), 160.1, 164.6 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.3 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) *m/z*: 537.10 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for $C_{28}H_{20}FN_7O_4$: C, 62.57; H, 3.75; N, 18.24. Found: C, 62.52; H, 3.61; N, 18.20 %.

4-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-6-methyl-5-(5-(4-nitrophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3g)

Yield: 66 %, m.p. 269-271 °C. IR (KBr): 3211 (NH), 3059 (C-H_{arom}), 2980 (H-C=C<), 2848 (C-H, CH₃), 1693 (C=O), 1598 (C=N), 1527 (C=C), 1504 (N=O), 1284 (C-O-C), 1157 (C-F) cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 2.40 (s, 3H, CH₃), 5.21 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.80 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 7.29-8.23 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 8.31 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.24 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃). ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 15.7 (CH₃), 54.7 (C_{pyrimidine}), 123.4 (C_{pyrazole}), 113.2-149.2 (Ar-C), 147.1 (C-NO₂), 150.6 (C=O), 160.4, 164.9 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.6 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) *m/z*: 537.13 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for $C_{28}H_{20}FN_7O_4$: C, 62.57; H, 3.75; N, 18.24. Found: C, 62.62; H, 3.78; N, 18.29 %.

4-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-5-(5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3h)

Yield: 68 %, m.p. 179-181 °C. IR (KBr): 3409 (OH), 3216 (NH), 3062 (C-H_{arom}), 2984 (H-C=C<), 2845 (C-H, CH₃), 1697 (C=O), 1602 (C=N), 1525 (C=C), 1280 (C-O-C), 1151 (C-F) cm^{-1} . ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆, δ ppm): 2.35 (s, 3H, CH₃), 5.22 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.82 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 7.02-8.07 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 8.18 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.16 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃), 9.20 (s, 1H,

OH). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 15.0 (CH₃), 53.4 (C_{pyrimidine}), 123.2 (C_{pyrazole}), 113.2-149.7 (Ar-C), 150.1 (C=O), 157.3 (C-OH), 160.1, 164.4 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.8 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) m/z : 508.16 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for C₂₈H₂₁FN₆O₃: C, 66.14; H, 4.16; N, 16.53. Found: C, 66.23; H, 4.12; N, 16.58 %.

4-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-5-(5-(3-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3i)

Yield: 57 %, m.p. 271-273 °C. IR (KBr): 3412 (OH), 3217 (NH), 3064 (C-H_{arom}), 2987 (H-C=C<), 2848 (C-H, CH₃), 1698 (C=O), 1609 (C=N), 1528 (C=C), 1252 (C-O-C), 1151 (C-F) cm⁻¹. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 2.34 (s, 3H, CH₃), 5.19 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.80 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 6.99-8.14 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 8.20 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.14 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃), 9.19 (s, 1H, OH). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 15.3 (CH₃), 53.1 (C_{pyrimidine}), 123.4 (C_{pyrazole}), 113.0-149.8 (Ar-C), 150.4 (C=O), 157.6 (C-OH), 164.3 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.2 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) m/z :

508.16 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for C₂₈H₂₁FN₆O₃: C, 66.14; H, 4.16; N, 16.53. Found: C, 66.26; H, 4.20; N, 16.61 %.

4-(3-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-5-(5-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-6-methyl-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-one (3j)

Yield: 73 %, m.p. 237-239 °C. IR (KBr): 3418 (OH), 3219 (NH), 3062 (C-H_{arom}), 2981 (H-C=C<), 2853 (C-H, CH₃), 1692 (C=O), 1605 (C=N), 1526 (C=C), 1278 (C-O-C), 1160 (C-F) cm⁻¹. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 2.37 (s, 3H, CH₃), 5.22 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrimidine}), 6.83 (s, 1H, NH-C-Ph), 6.96-8.17 (m, 13H, Ar-H), 8.21 (s, 1H, CH_{pyrazole}), 9.16 (s, 1H, NH-C-CH₃), 9.20 (s, 1H, OH). ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 15.0 (CH₃), 53.3 (C_{pyrimidine}), 123.0 (C_{pyrazole}), 113.6-149.9 (Ar-C), 150.6 (C=O), 158.4 (C-OH), 160.6, 164.7 (C_{oxadiazole}), 161.8 (C-F). LCMS (ESI) m/z : 508.16 [M]⁺. Anal. calcd. for C₂₈H₂₁FN₆O₃: C, 66.14; H, 4.16; N, 16.53. Found: C, 66.19; H, 4.22; N, 16.60 %.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis of compounds of interest is shown in Scheme 1. The synthesis of compound 2 used the familiar Biginelli reaction with diaryl-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde and the subsequent addition of NH₂-NH₂ (hydrazine hydrate). The final compounds were produced by treating this adduct with various aryl acid derivatives in a one-pot reaction. The chemical compound 4-(3-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-phenyl-1-hydrazole-6-methyl-5-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)-1) Hydrophobic rimidin-2numbers 3a-o.

The in vitro antibacterial activity of the synthesised compounds was assessed after they were characterised using well-established spectroscopic methods. The compound 3a-o exhibited a distinct absorption band at 1710-1680 cm⁻¹ in its infrared spectra, which is indicative of the carbonyl group. Additionally, a band at 3293-3212 cm⁻¹ was seen, which corresponds to a secondary amine. The aromatic ring's C-H stretching, H-C=C<, and -CH₃ were accompanied by vibrations at 3151-3058, 2998-2978, and 2929-2845 cm⁻¹, respectively. The aromatic ring's >C=N- and >C=C< stretching is shown by absorption bands at 1609-1592, 1533-1500 cm⁻¹, and the oxadiazole ring's C-O-C stretching is shown by absorption bands at 1289-1217 cm⁻¹.

The three singlet peaks seen in ^1H NMR at δ = 2.26-2.40, 5.17-5.45, and 9.04-9.24 ppm, respectively, were caused by three protons: one from the methyl group, one from the -CH of the pyrimidine ring, and one from the -NH of the pyrimidine ring (-NH-C-CH₃). It was one proton of the -NH group in the pyrimidine ring (-NH-C-Ph) that caused the singlet signal at δ = 6.80-7.06 ppm to arise. A distinct signal at δ = 150.2-151.3 ppm, attributed to the carbonyl carbon of the pyrimidine scaffold, and an additional signal at δ = 15.0-15.2 ppm, attributed to the carbon of the methyl group, were seen in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound 3a-o. The mass spectra also revealed fragment peaks and a molecular ion peak matching molecular formula 3a-o, both of which were in conformity with the predicted chemical structure and molecular weight.

Scheme 1. Synthetic pathway of novel compounds 3a-o

Figure 1. Plausible mechanistic pathway of synthesized analogs

Figure 1 suggests a possible mechanism of action for compounds 3a-o. After undergoing an intermolecular nucleophilic attack on the carbonyl carbon of various aromatic acids (2), Biginelli hydrazide (1) was converted to targeted compounds (6) by cyclocondensation (the elimination of HCl) (5) in the presence of phosphorus oxychloride (POCl₃).

Antimicrobial activity

A number of the 3a-o synthesised compounds showed antibacterial effects ranging from fair to exceptional. Compounds 3j (-4-OH-C₆H₄), 3k (-4-OCH₃-C₆H₄), and 3l (-4-CH₃-C₆H₄) outperformed the gold standard drugs chloramphenicol and Ciprofloxacin in antibacterial screenings conducted against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, and *S. pyogenes*, as shown in Table 1. Using Nystatin and Griseofulvin as reference standards, the antifungal activity MIC values were measured using the usual broth microdilution bioassay technique.²⁴ At a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of 12.5 μg mL⁻¹, compounds 3h (-2-OH-C₆H₄) and 3l (-4-CH₃-C₆H₄) had an impressive inhibitory action against the chosen fungal strains.

Antitubercular and cytotoxic activity

The in vitro antitubercular activity of the synthesised oxadiazole hybrid molecules 3a-o was tested using the microplate alamar blue assay (MABA) against the Mycobacterium TB H37Rv strain in BACTEC 12B medium, at a concentration of 6.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. In the first round of testing, drugs that demonstrated 90% inhibition or above were retested at concentrations below 6.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ using 2-fold dilution to establish the specific MIC. Compounds 3d, 3h, 3j, 3k, and 3l showed a range of 92% to 98% inhibition of Mtb in early in vitro screening. The second round of screening involves

The MIC for Mtb inhibition by compounds 3j (-4-OH-C₆H₄) and 3l (-4-CH₃-C₆H₄) was 0.03 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, which is identical to the MIC for isoniazid, the reference standard.

The cytotoxicity (IC₅₀) of compounds with relatively low MICs was assessed in VERO cell lines. The following formula was used to compute their selectivity index (SI): IC₅₀/MIC. In comparison to 3d and 3k, the toxicity of chemicals 3h, 3j, and 3l was lower. In general, compounds 3j and 3l are potential bioactive molecules for future investigation since they have MIC $\leq$ 6.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and SI $\geq$ 10. Additionally, the newly synthesised compound may be deemed to have good leadership with MIC $\leq$ 1 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The data from the antitubercular trials, as well as the compounds' real IC₅₀ and SI, are shown in Table 2.

Determination of 50 % IC₅₀ in VERO cells (Cytotoxicity assay)

The IC₅₀ value for cytotoxicity in VERO cells was measured using compounds at concentrations below or equal to 62.5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, which is 10 times the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for M. tuberculosis H37Rv. Using the Promega CellTiter 96 Non-radioactive Cell Proliferation Assay, the viability was evaluated after 72 hours of exposure by measuring the cellular conversion of MTT into a formazan product. Additionally, we calculated the Selectivity Index (SI) as IC₅₀/MIC; a SI greater than 10 was deemed statistically significant.

Structure-activity relationship study

The electronic localization of molecular hankerings was achieved in this paper by use of 1,3,4-oxadiazole motifs. An increase in biological potency was seen when an electron-withdrawing substituent was utilised, in contrast to an electron-releasing group on the phenyl nucleus of 1,3,4-oxadiazole.

Table 1. Antimicrobial screening of the compounds **3a-o**.

No.	-Ar	MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATIONS, MIC, in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$						
		Gram-negative		Gram-positive		Fungi		
		<i>E.C.</i> ^a	<i>P.A.</i> ^b	<i>S.A.</i> ^c	<i>S.P.</i> ^d	<i>C.A.</i> ^e	<i>A.N.</i> ^f	<i>A.C.</i> ^g
3a	-C ₆ H ₅	500	250	500	250	500	N.A. ^h	N.A.
3b	-2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	125	250	500	100	500	NA.	NA.
3c	-3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	100	100	100	500	NA.	NA.	500
3d	-4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	25	62.5	25	100	500	NA.	NA.
3e	-2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	1000	500	500	500	NA.	250	NA.
3f	-3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	1000	1000	500	500	250	100	250
3g	-4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	500	100	1000	1000	500	NA.	NA.
3h	-2-OH-C ₆ H ₄	100	1000	1000	500	NA.	100	12.5
3i	-3-OH-C ₆ H ₄	1000	100	500	50	NA.	1000	NA.
3j	-4-OH-C ₆ H ₄	12.5	25	1000	100	1000	1000	100
3k	-4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	100	250	500	12.5	50	1000	1000
3l	-4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	500	500	25	1000	100	12.5	NA.
3m	-CH ₂ NHCOC ₆ H ₅	1000	1000	250	500	1000	NA.	50
3n	-CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	500	1000	100	500	NA.	50	1000
3o	-C ₂ H ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	1000	500	250	1000	1000	500	1000
S.d.ⁱ 1	Chloramphenicol	50	50	50	50	-	-	-
S.d. 2	Ciprofloxacin	25	25	50	50	-	-	-
S.d. 3	Nystatin	-	-	-	-	100	100	100
S.d. 4	Griseofulvin	-	-	-	-	500	100	100

^a*E.C.*: *Escherichia coli* MTCC 443; ^b*P.A.*: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* MTCC 1688; ^c*S.A.*: *Staphylococcus aureus* MTCC 96; ^d*S.P.*: *Staphylococcus pyogenes* MTCC 442; ^e*C.A.*: *Candida albicans* MTCC 227; ^f*A.N.*: *Aspergillus niger* MTCC 282; ^g*A.C.*: *Aspergillus clavatus* MTCC 1323; ^hN.A.: No activity; ⁱS.d.: Standard drug.

Table 2. *In vitro* antitubercular screening data of oxadiazole analogs **3a-o**.

No.	-Ar	% Inhibition, at 6.25 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$	MIC ^a , $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$	IC ₅₀ ^b VERO cells	SI ^c =IC ₅₀ /MIC
3a	-C ₆ H ₅	65	n.d. ^f	n.d.	n.d.
3b	-2-ClC ₆ H ₄	55	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
3c	-3-ClC ₆ H ₄	52	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
3d	-4-ClC ₆ H ₄	92	6.25	7.2	1.15
3e	-2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	48	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
3f	-3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	71	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
3g	-4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	62	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
3h	-2-HOC ₆ H ₄	93	3.13	>10	>3.19
3i	-3-HOC ₆ H ₄	82	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
3j	-4-HOC ₆ H ₄	98	0.03	>10	333
3k	-4-MeOC ₆ H ₄	96	1.56	8.9	5.70
3l	-4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	97	0.03	>10	333
3m	-CH ₂ NHCOC ₆ H ₅	81	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
3n	-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	73	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
3o	-C ₂ H ₂ C ₆ H ₅	84	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
R.S.^d	INH ^e	99	0.03	-	-

^aMinimum inhibitory concentration against H₃₇Rv strain of *M. tuberculosis* ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). ^bMeasurement of cytotoxicity in VERO cells: 50% inhibitory concentrations ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$). ^cSelectivity index (*in vitro*): IC₅₀ in VERO cells/MIC against *M. tuberculosis*. ^dR.S.: Reference Standard; ^eINH: Isoniazid; ^fn.d.: Not determined.

Compounds **3h**, **3j**, **3k** and **3l**, substituted with inductively electron-donating groups like methyl, methoxy (on *para*) and hydroxyl (on *ortho* and *para*), showed the maximum inhibitory antimicrobial as well as antitubercular influence with an IC_{50} of $>10 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Looking at the MIC values, it may be concluded that electron-donating groups at the *para* position of the phenyl ring induced a positive effect on bio- activity.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study was to create new structural hybrids that combine DHPMs with pyrazole clubbed 1,3,4-oxadiazole; these compounds have the potential to be effective against tuberculosis and other microbes. It follows from the biological activity that these compounds' structural and electronic diversity affect their action. The most effective antimicrobials and antitubercular candidates were scaffolds **3h**, **3j**, **3k**, and **3l** that included an electron-donating group like -OH, -OCH₃, or -CH₃. Also, the cytotoxicity was somewhat low when the most active molecules (**3j** and **3l**) were transported. The results might be novel, very effective antimicrobials and antitubercular scaffolds that are reasonably easy to produce using this hybrid nucleus.

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